

KHRS26 (KHP5) for upland direct-seeded conditions

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Rainfed kharif rice is the major field crop in the hill zone of Karnataka (11°56' and 15°46' N latitude and 74°31' and 76°4' E longitude). Rainfall in the zone ranges from 1,363 to 3,426 mm, with an average of 2,173 mm. Rice is grown as a drill-sown crop in the uplands and, to some extent, in the midlands, where rainfall is medium to low; it is mostly a transplanted crop in the lowlands. Crop area in the zone is 284,700 ha, with an annual production of 723,000 t. It represents nearly 23% of the rice area in the state. The average production in the zone is lower (2.5 t ha⁻¹) than that of the state (3 t ha⁻¹).

Jaya, G318, and Karna are the three varieties recommended for direct sowing in the hill zone. Attempts were made at the RRS during the mid-1980s to identify a suitable variety for the region. Of the selections obtained from the cross Intan/IET7191, KHRS26 was the most promising in station trials. It was further tested in farm trials for 3 yr. Based on its superior performance, the variety was released for commercial cultivation in 1998.

Farmers usually prefer semitall varieties with medium bold grain for drill-sown situations in the uplands. KHRS26 was readily accepted because it yielded 17–27% more grain and 13–14% more fodder in the station (Table 1) compared with the checks, in addition to meeting farmers' preferences for plant height and grain quality.

KHRS26 is suitable for upland direct-seeded situations, having an optimum duration of 150–155 d (Table 2). Early maturing varieties are usually harvestable during the rainy season and are also more attractive to birds.

The variety had an 11% higher yield than the checks (Table 3) in farmers' fields (tested in 19 locations across 4 districts).

Table 1. Performance of KHRS26 in upland rice variety trial (direct-seeded) at the Regional Research Station, Mudigere, 1991-96.

Entry	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)					Av	% increase over check	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹) ^b	% increase over check
	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995				
KHRS26	1.3	3.9	3.6	4.8	2.6	3.2		4.3	
G318 ^a	1.0	2.6	1.6	3.7	2.8	2.4	27	3.8	13
Karna ^a	1.2	2.6	1.9	3.7	2.4	2.4	27	3.7	13
Jaya ^a	1.3	2.8	2.8	3.4	3.1	2.7	17	3.6	14
Mean	1.3	3.5	2.5	3.6	2.8			3.7	
CD (5%)	0.17	0.82	0.36	0.62	0.45			0.40	
CV (%)	6	14	9	10	10			7	

^aRecommended varieties used as checks. ^b1996 data.

Table 2. Comparison of KHRS26 with check varieties for yield attributes in upland rice variety trial (direct-seeded), 1991-96.

Entry	Days to flowering	Plant height (cm)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Grain type	1,000-grain weight (g)
KHRS26	125	85–90	260	19.1	Medium bold	27.6
G318 ^a	110	60–65	265	17.7	Long bold	26.2
Karna ^a	115	65–70	260	18.2	Medium bold	25.0
Jaya ^a	115	65–70	265	18.1	Medium bold	27.5

^aRecommended varieties used as checks.

Table 3. Performance of KHRS26 in farm trials (direct-seeded), 1994-96.

Entry	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)				% increase over check
	1994 (5) ^a	1995 (8)	1996 (6)	Av (19)	
KHRS26	3.9	4.2	5.3	4.5	
Check ^b	3.2	3.9	4.9	4.0	11

^aNumbers in parentheses represent number of test locations. ^bRecommended varieties used as checks.

International Workshop on Characterizing and Understanding Rainfed Rice Environments scheduled for December 1999

IRRI, in partnership with national agricultural research systems in several Asian countries, has been carrying out studies to understand rainfed rice environments as well as evaluate cropping practices to translate research into appropriate technological interventions. This research ranges from broad, regional-scale characterization to detailed farm-level studies. Studies have been and are being carried out in different geographical areas by different institutions. Different methodologies have been tested, and several cross-cutting issues have emerged. These and other findings and conclusions will be discussed in the Rainfed Lowland Rice Research Consortium (RLRRC) workshop to be held on 6-10 December 1999 at Bali, Indonesia. The workshop aims to bring together researchers involved in characterizing rainfed rice environments, to review the progress in research related to characterization of the rainfed rice environment, including work carried out at RLRRC sites, and identify needs and opportunities for using characterization work for research prioritization and planning of the Consortium's future research activities. Characterization was chosen as the theme for this year's workshop.

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